

**ACTIVE ISSUES OF FORMING IDEOLOGICAL
IMMUNITY IN THE MIND OF YOUTH****Abdujabborova Rukhshona**

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Email: rabdujabborova49@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19979150>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th April 2026Accepted: 28th April 2026Online: 30th April 2026**KEYWORDS***ideological immunity, youth, globalization, information security, spiritual education***ABSTRACT**

This article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of forming ideological immunity among youth. In the context of globalization, the growing influence of information attacks and destructive ideas makes the protection of youth consciousness a pressing issue. The study highlights the concept, structure, and mechanisms of ideological immunity formation. It also examines the role of education, family, and society in this process.

Introduction. In the context of today's globalization processes, the integration of social, political and information space is developing rapidly worldwide. On the one hand, this process serves to expand science, technology and intercultural contacts, but on the other hand, it creates the basis for the unlimited spread of various harmful ideas, alien ideologies and spiritual threats. In particular, the activity of the youth on social networks and digital platforms makes them direct consumers of various information flows and sometimes objects of influence. As a result of the rapid development of modern information and communication technologies, the speed and volume of information receipt have increased to an unprecedented level. However, not all information has reliable, objective and positive content. Various manipulative information, materials promoting false values, and propaganda tools aimed at instilling extremist and radical ideas can have a negative impact on the minds of young people. In this regard, ensuring information security, especially protecting the younger generation from harmful information, is emerging as one of the most pressing issues of our time.

The formation of ideological immunity in the minds of young people serves not only to protect them from the influence of foreign ideas, but also to develop their ability to think independently, increase their social activity, and ensure their maturity as individuals committed to national and universal values. Young people with ideological immunity are able to critically analyze any information, understand its content, and consciously draw the right conclusions. Therefore, this issue has risen to the level of state policy and requires close cooperation between the education system, the family institution, civil society, and the media. After all, the formation of a healthy ideological environment in the minds of young people is one of the important factors for the stability of society, national security, and future development.

Ideological immunity is a complex socio-psychological phenomenon that expresses a person's ability to consciously resist various alien, harmful and destructive ideas, to critically

analyze them and draw independent conclusions. This concept reflects not only a defense mechanism, but also the strength of a person's internal spiritual stability, beliefs and worldview. A person with ideological immunity selectively accepts any information, deeply understands its content and essence, and can clearly define his position in relation to various ideological influences.

The essence of ideological immunity is that it ensures a person's intellectual independence, protects him from manipulation and information pressure, and serves the formation of a person on the basis of spiritual and moral values. In this process, it is important for a person not only to have existing knowledge, but also to be able to apply it in practice, to form an analytical approach to events. Therefore, ideological immunity is not just a set of theoretical knowledge, but also a complex system that is inextricably linked with life experience, social environment and upbringing. The components of ideological immunity are closely interconnected and consist of the following:

Firstly, the knowledge system includes the historical, political, legal and cultural literacy of a person. Young people who have historical memory, know their national statehood and cultural heritage are more stable in relation to various foreign ideas. Political and legal knowledge, on the other hand, helps to form civic consciousness and understand a person's place in society.

Secondly, the value system is determined by a person's respect for national traditions and customs, and loyalty to universal human values. It is values that serve as a person's internal "filter", through which various information and ideas are evaluated. A person with a strong value system is stable against foreign cultural and spiritual influences.

Thirdly, social activity means that a person actively participates in the life of society, has a civic position and is not indifferent to social processes. Socially active young people freely express their opinions, contribute to the development of society and consciously fight against various harmful ideas.

Fourthly, critical thinking is one of the most important components of ideological immunity, which means the ability to analyze information, assess its reliability and draw objective conclusions. A person with critical thinking quickly perceives various manipulative information, false propaganda and false information and forms an independent position in relation to them.

Thus, ideological immunity is a complex system formed on the basis of a person's knowledge, values, social activity and critical thinking, which is an important factor in protecting young people from various ideological threats. Its formation requires a continuous educational process, a social environment and the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work. Ideological threats in the context of globalization. Along with the globalization process, threats such as "mass culture", extremist ideas, information manipulation are also becoming widespread. These threats especially quickly affect the minds of young people, because they are the most active consumers of the flow of information.

The main manifestations of ideological threats: Harmful information spread through the Internet and social networks; False values and elements of "mass culture"; Religious extremism and radicalism; Information wars and propaganda influences.

Mechanisms for the formation of ideological immunity. The formation of ideological immunity in the minds of young people is a multifaceted process, and the following factors are of great importance:

1. The role of the education system. It is important to develop independent thinking of young people in educational institutions, strengthen historical memory, and instill national values. Ideological education is especially effective through social sciences.

2. The importance of the family institution. The family is the main link in the upbringing of young people, and the values formed in it play an important role throughout the life of a person. The spiritual level and educational approach of parents directly affect the formation of ideological immunity.

3. Mass media and the Internet. Creating a healthy environment in the information space, increasing reliable and useful content are important in protecting young people from harmful information. Improving media literacy is also an effective tool in this regard.

4. Harmonizing national and universal values. Awareness of national identity, respect for historical heritage, and instilling universal values in the minds of young people ensure ideological stability.

Current problems and their solutions. In today's conditions of globalization and the rapid development of the digital information space, the process of forming ideological immunity in the minds of young people is associated with a number of complex problems. These problems are manifested as factors affecting the spiritual stability of not only the education system, but also the entire society. First of all, one of the current problems is the insufficient formation of critical information analysis skills among young people. Although modern young people are faced with a large flow of information, they do not have the opportunity to evaluate all of them based on an analytical approach. As a result, in some cases they may fall under the influence of false information, manipulative messages or targeted propaganda. This negatively affects their worldview and social position. The second important problem is the widespread use of harmful content on the Internet. Today, extremist ideas, materials promoting violence, and content contrary to moral standards are rapidly reaching the general public, especially the youth, through various social networks and platforms. Such information can negatively affect the psyche and value system of young people and hinder their spiritual development. The third problem is related to the superficial and formal conduct of educational work in some cases. In some cases, spiritual and educational activities are organized only within the framework of formality, and insufficient attention is paid to their content and effectiveness. As a result, these activities do not penetrate deeply into the minds of young people and do not produce the expected results. Eliminating these problems requires a comprehensive and systematic approach. First of all, it is important to increase media literacy. By teaching young people to select, verify and analyze information, they can be protected from various harmful influences. In this regard, it is advisable to include subjects and modules related to media literacy in educational programs, and organize practical training. The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies is also an important solution. Through interactive methods, problem-based learning, debates, case studies and project approaches, it is possible to develop independent thinking and analytical abilities of young people. This, in turn, strengthens their ideological stability. In

addition, it is necessary to strengthen the system of individual work with young people. Working on the basis of an individual approach, taking into account the interests, worldview and problems of each young person, has a positive effect on their social and spiritual development. In this process, it is important to effectively use the system of psychological services, mentoring and tutoring. Another important direction is the systematic and effective organization of spiritual and educational events. Such events should be organized based on modern forms and methods, taking into account the interests and needs of young people. Especially interactive and practically oriented activities have a strong impact on the minds of young people.

Conclusion. The formation of ideological immunity in the minds of young people is an important factor in the stability and development of society. This process requires a continuous, systematic and comprehensive approach. Spiritual and educational work carried out in cooperation with the education system, family and society is of great importance in protecting young people from various ideological threats.

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